

ДАНИ ПРО АВТОРА

Кучеренко Світлана Юріївна, кандидат економічних наук, доцент кафедри економіки, ДВНЗ «Переяслав-Хмельницький ДПУ імені Григорія Сковороди»
вул. Сухомлинського 30, м. Переяслав-Хмельницький, 08401, Україна

ДАННЫЕ ОБ АВТОРЕ

Кучеренко Светлана Юрьевна, кандидат экономических наук, доцент кафедры экономики ГВУЗ «Переяслав-Хмельницкий ГПУ имени Григория Сковороды»
ул. Сухомлинского, 30, г. Переяслав-Хмельницкий, 08401, Украина

DATA ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Kucherenko Svitlana Yuriivna, PhD, assistant professor of Economics Department, Pereiaslav-Khmelnytskyi Hryhorii Skovoroda State Pedagogical University
30, Sukhomlynsky Str., Pereyaslav-Khmelnytsky, Kyiv Region, 08401, Ukraine.

УДК 338. 48 : [001.895: 005.336.3]

**ІННОВАЦІЙНА СИСТЕМА УПРАВЛІННЯ ЯКІСТЮ СФЕРИ ОБСЛУГОВУВАННЯ
ЯК ОBOB'ЯЗKOBA СКЛАДОВА РОЗВИТКУ ТУРИЗМУ**

**Танана С.М.,
Сергійчук О.М.**

***Предметом** дослідження є теоретичні та практичні питання застосування інноваційних систем управління якістю сфери обслуговування.*

***Мета** статті полягає в аналізі інноваційної системи управління якістю сфери обслуговування та її ролі в активізації розвитку туризму.*

***Методи дослідження.** У статті застосовано методи теоретичного узагальнення і порівняння, системного аналізу.*

***Результати роботи.** Активізація сфери туристичних послуг зумовлює необхідність розробки та впровадження системи управління якістю як обов'язкової складової стратегії розвитку як туризму в цілому, так і на рівні його окремих підприємств. Найреальнішим способом досягнення цієї мети є формування механізму державного регулювання та управління якістю туристичних послуг, що має бути спрямованим на всебічне цілеспрямоване використання заходів, систем та методів управління. Система управління якістю обслуговування в процесі впровадження й удосконалення органічно взаємодіє з іншими соціальними й виробничими системами підприємств туристичної індустрії. У першу чергу це управління розробкою туристичного продукту, плануванням виробництва, технологічною підготовкою, матеріальними та фінансовими ресурсами, якістю праці, підготовкою кадрів тощо. Сукупно ці системи охоплюють усі сфери діяльності трудового колективу туристичного підприємства: виробничу, економічну, соціальну, технологічну.*

Досягнення ефективності системи управління якістю обслуговування на підприємствах туристичної індустрії не може бути забезпечено без використання різних інноваційних форм й активного впливу обслуговуючого та управлінського персоналу на підвищення якості обслуговування туристів, туристичних агентів.

***Галузь застосування результатів.** Отримані результати створюють теоретичне підґрунтя для активізації інноваційної діяльності на вітчизняній системі управління якістю сфери обслуговування.*

***Висновки.** Якість обслуговування впливає на структуру споживчого попиту і є важливим чинником у конкурентній боротьбі на туристичному ринку в сучасних умовах господарювання. Туристи, які задоволені сферою обслуговуванням у готелях, ресторанах, екскурсійних бюро, туристичних фірмах, стають їх активними пропагандистами. На якість обслуговування впливають такі фактори, як комплексність послуг і товарів, їх направленість на конкретного споживача, своєчасність їх надання.*

***Ключові слова:** сфера обслуговування, забезпечення якості, управління якістю, поліпшення якості, організаційні інновації, маркетингові інновації, періодичні інновації.*

ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ СИСТЕМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВОМ СФЕРЫ ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ КАК ОБЯЗАТЕЛЬНАЯ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИЗМА

Танана С.М.,
Сергийчук Е.Н.

Предметом исследование является теоретические и практические вопросы использования инновационных систем управления качеством сферы обслуживания.

Цель статьи заключается в анализе инновационной системы управления качеством сферы обслуживания и ее роли в активизации развития туризма.

Методы исследования. В статье применены методы теоретического обобщения и сравнения, системного анализа.

Результаты работы. Активизация сферы туристических услуг обуславливает необходимость разработки и внедрения системы управления качеством как обязательной составляющей стратегии развития как туризма в целом, так и на уровне его отдельных предприятий. Реальным способом достижения этой цели является формирование механизма государственного регулирования и управления качеством туристических услуг, который должен быть направленным на всестороннее целенаправленное использование мер, систем и методов управления. Система управления качеством обслуживания в процессе внедрения и совершенствования органично взаимодействует с другими социальными и производственными системами предприятий туристической индустрии. В первую очередь это управление разработкой туристического продукта, планированием производства, технологической подготовкой, материальными и финансовыми ресурсами, качеством труда, подготовкой кадров. Совокупно эти системы охватывают все сферы деятельности трудового коллектива туристического предприятия: производственную, экономическую, социальную, технологическую. Достижения эффективности системы управления качеством обслуживания на предприятиях туристической индустрии не может быть обеспечено без использования различных инновационных форм и активного влияния обслуживающего и управленческого персонала на повышение качества обслуживания туристов, туристических агентов.

Область применения результатов. Полученные результаты создают теоретическую основу для активизации инновационной деятельности на отечественной системе управления качеством сферы обслуживания.

Выводы. Качество обслуживания влияет на структуру потребительского спроса и является важным фактором в конкурентной борьбе на туристическом рынке в современных условиях хозяйствования. Туристы, которые довольны сферой обслуживанием в отелях, ресторанах, экскурсионных бюро, туристических фирмах, становятся их активными пропагандистами. На качество обслуживания влияют такие факторы, как комплексность услуг и товаров, их направленность на конкретного потребителя, своевременность их предоставления.

Ключевые слова: сфера обслуживания, обеспечение качества, управление качеством, улучшение качества, организационные инновации, маркетинговые инновации, периодические инновации.

INNOVATION SYSTEM OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF SERVICES SECTOR AS COMPULSORY COMPONENT OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

Olena Sergiichuk
Svitlana Tanana

The subject of research is theoretical and practical questions of using of innovative systems of quality management of system the services sector.

The purpose of the article – to analyze the innovative system of quality management system service sector and it role in activization of development tourism.

Methods of the research. Methods of theoretical generalization and comparison, system analysis are used in the article.

The results of the research. Activization of tourist services sector determines of necessity the development and implementation of quality management system as compulsory component of the development strategy as tourism as a whole and at the level of the individual companies. The most real method to achieve this purpose is the formation of mechanism of state regulation and quality management of tourist services, should directed to the full using of measures, systems and methods of management. System of services sector of quality management in the implementation and improvement interacts with

other social systems and industrial enterprises of the tourism industry. The first is the management of development of the tourism product, production planning, technological preparation, material and financial resources, quality of work, preparation of personnel. Together, these systems cover all spheres of activity the labour collective of tourist enterprise, industrial, economical, social, technological.

Achieving of effectiveness system of the management quality of services sector on enterprises of the tourism industry can't achieved without the using of various innovative forms and active influence of services sector and management personnel on improve of the quality of tourist services, tourist agents.

Field of using results. *The results providing create of a theoretical basis for activization of innovation activity in the national quality management system of services sector.*

Conclusions. *Quality of services sector affects on the structure and consumer demand is an important factor in competition on the tourism market in the modern economic conditions. Tourists of the services sector at hotels, restaurants, travel agencies, travel agencies, active advocates are satisfied. On quality of services sector is influenced of such factor as the directing on services and products, their orientation to a specific consumer.*

Key words: *services sector, assurance of quality, management of quality, quality improvement, organizational innovations, marketing innovations, periodic innovations.*

Actuality of the theme. The Ukrainian Innovation Development Strategy for 2010-2020 years, in the context of globalization trends and modern challenges, Ukrainian higher education should professionally prepare people for life in the information society, society of knowledge and innovation, to form a person with innovative thinking, innovative culture, and ability to innovate activity, which becomes a guarantee of the competitiveness of the national economy [5]. All of these requirements directly affect the process of professional preparation for tourism.

Creation of a new educational system, adapted to the dynamic changes, taking place in tourism in the conditions of an innovative economic formation, has a priority task in most European countries. As you know, tourism is a unique kind of activity; it is characterized by globalization, sustainable development and positive economic results. Globalization, the growth of tourist flows put of new requirements for tourism education: the availability of the only professional qualifications of tourism activity, knowledge of foreign languages, culture, and economics, legal and social systems of partner-countries.

The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), which supports education, conducts educational programs for tourism, a significant role in solving the problem of preparation specialists are played. In last years, identification has emerged in the field of tourism and in the preparation of specialists system with a large number of specializations that reflect the diversity of tourist services and take into account the prospects for rapid development of the industry.

The integration process at the corresponding stages is to implement European norms and standards in education, tourism, distribution of native cultural and scientific-technical achievements in the European Union. Eventually, such steps will work on increase the European cultural identity in Ukraine and integration to European intellectual, educational and scientific and technical environment. The management of the State Tourism Administration of Ukraine sees one of the significant steps in the development of the industry in controlling the quality of tourist services provided to the client [4].

Today in Ukraine there are about 3 thousand enterprises that have received licenses for tourism activities. According to official figures, 75% of them are engaged in tourist activities in a part-time. That is, from time to time, and the image of Ukraine on the world tourist market depends on the quality of the tourist product (services) offered by tourist enterprises (firms), and not on their quantity. Quality of activity (service) depends from professionalism, qualification, experience of personnel of tourist enterprises (firms).

In order to change Ukraine into a world-class tourist country, it is necessary to ensure coordination of the activities of the economic sectors on which the quality provision of tourist services depends. It is a hotel industry, transport, trade, communication, etc.

Another important motive for the arrival of foreign tourists to Ukraine is the natural resources and historical-cultural heritage of our country. The cost of natural resources and historical-cultural monuments depends on their availability and qualitative characteristics. Depending on the degree of accessibility of these resources and their exploitation for the purpose of tourism, they will become of great economic importance for Ukraine [6, p. 21].

The activation of the tourism services sector necessitates the development and implementation of a quality management system (QMS) as an integral part of the development strategy of tourism in general and at the level of its individual enterprises. The most realistic way to achieve this goal is formation a mechanism of state regulation and management of the quality of tourist services, which should directed at the comprehensive, purposeful using of measures, systems and management methods [3].

In the tourist-excursion business in Ukraine, a long time monopolized the state and customers had to put up with what they offered. Today, the situation is changing, and there are numerous private tourism companies, which are still mainly engaged in the organization of foreign travel. But not far off is the time when foreigners are attracted to Ukrainian routes. In these circumstances, healthy competition plays a positive role, which will force tour companies to set up their business in order to have regular customers and to do so provide them with high-quality and diverse services, taking into account the diverse tastes and cultural and aesthetic needs of consumers.

Numerous researches on improving the system of strategic management by higher education of modern information technologies, management of innovative potential (T. Bogolib, L. Haiduk, V. Hryga, L. Kozarezenko, I. Yegorov, L. Hrytsenko, O. Parkhomenko, G. Androshchuk, O. Herasymenko, V. Shchekunov); providing information on higher education (L. Zainutdinova, I. Zakharova, Ye. Polat, I. Robert, A. Smirnov, V. Soldakin); generalization of different approaches of scientists to the definition of the essence of the notion «informational and educational environment of higher education» (B. Akhmetov, A. Kaliuzhniy, O. Kosolapov, V. Kriukov, A. Torina, K. Shahgeldian); organizational aspects of introduction in the educational process of new information technologies (S. Bondareva, V. Bykov, T. Gabai, M. Zhaldak, P. Korchemnyi, O. Spivakovskiy), made of base for successful solution of problem the information of higher education as complex organization, technical and technological process of development and introduction of information system of higher school.

Management of the quality of tourist services should be carried out systematically, that is, at the enterprises – subjects of the tourist industry should operate a system of quality management of tourist services. Such a system is an organizational structure with a clear distribution of responsibilities, procedures, processes and resources that are needed to manage the quality of a tourist product. World experience has formed not only general features of existing quality management systems, but also principles and methods that can be applied in each of them [2, p. 125]. There are three types of quality control systems that have conceptual differences: systems that meet the requirements of ISO 9000 series standards: General Quality Management Systems (TQM – Total Quality Management); systems that meet the criteria for national or international (regional) awards, diplomas in quality of service sector [8].

The life cycle of services includes all stages of its existence: from the initial definition of requirements and needs of the consumer to their ultimate satisfaction. The life cycle according of ISO 9004: 2009 is schematically provided by a loop or quality spiral [4]. Thus, when managing the quality of travel services, it is advisable to distinguish between «quality assurance», «quality management» and «quality improvement» in accordance with ISO 9001: 2008 [3].

Quality Assurance is a set of planned and systematic measures necessary to ensure that the service meets certain quality requirements. Quality Control (Quality Control) is a coordinated effort to direct and monitor the organization's performance in relation to quality [8]. Typically, quality management is represented by a system of methods and measures that are implemented to meet quality requirements. Of course, this concept is recommended to be used with refinement definitions such as Quality Management in Manufacturing (Manufacturing Quality Control) or Quality Management at Company Level (Company – Wide Quality Control).

Quality management includes methods and activities of operational nature, aimed at simultaneously managing the process and eliminating the reasons for poor functioning at the appropriate stages of quality.

Improvement of quality (Quality Improvement) is a continuous activity aimed at increasing the technical level of products, the quality of its manufacturing, the improvement of the elements of production and quality system. Appointment of continuous improvement of the quality management system – increasing the probability of satisfaction of customers and other interested parties [8]. In accordance with the national state standard SSGU 9000 2007, «improvement actions include: analysis and assessment of the status quo for the definition of areas of improvement; setting goals for improvement; search for possible solutions for achieving goals; assessment of these decisions and the election of one of them; introduction of the chosen decision; measuring, checking, analyzing and evaluating the implementation results to determine whether the goals have been achieved; making changes». The combination and coordination of assurance, management and improvement of quality is the activity in the quality system of services.

The General Quality Management (Quality Management) is a component of a general management function that defines and ensures a quality policy. This management function includes: operational planning, resource allocation, and other systematic actions in the field of quality, such as quality planning, performance and performance evaluation.

The system of quality management in the process of implementation and improvement organically interacts with other social and industrial systems of enterprises of the tourism industry. First and foremost, it is the management of the development of a tourism product (routes, tours), production planning, technological

training, material and financial resources, quality of work, training, etc. Taken together, these systems cover all sectors of the labour collective of the tourist enterprise: production, economic, social, and technological.

Achievement of the efficiency of the quality management system at the enterprises of the tourism industry can not be achieved without the use of various innovative forms and the active influence of the service and management personnel on improving the quality of service of tourists, travel agents and counterparties:

1. *Implementation of innovations* (organizational innovations) that are related to the development of entrepreneurship and tourism business in the system and management structure, including reorganization, absorption of competing subjects on the basis of new technology and advanced technologies, personnel policy, rational economic and financial activities;

2. *Marketing innovations*, its can meet the needs of target customers, or attract new customers;

3. *Periodic innovations* (food innovations) aimed at changing the consumer qualities of a tourism product, its positioning on the market.

Today, the most important characteristic of innovation is its novelty, which promotes: the expansion of the range of potential consumers (tourists); change of pounds of consumer and expansion of function tourist product [7, p. 49].

Innovation in tourism should include, first of all, those innovations that are accompanied by:

- restore and development of spiritual and physical forces of tourists;
- qualitatively new changes in tourist products;
- increase in the efficiency of the tourism infrastructure;
- increase of efficiency of management of sustainable operation and development of tourist sphere in the country;
- increase of efficiency of processes of formation, positioning and consumption of tourist services;
- progressive changes in the factors of production;
- increase of image and competitiveness of enterprises of the tourist industry.

The large automation and internalization of the information space of the society reveals the horizons of attractive resorts, places for recreation and stimulates consumers to independently choose the route of travel, search for affordable services at the lowest prices and provide proactive communication with service providers, which translates the business of tourist organizers into the virtual sector.

This sector of travel, backed by the achievements of the Internet-industry, ensures the functioning of the network information space, especially in travel agency for the sale of bundled offers (tour operator and travel agency).

In addition to the real sector of the product sales of the international tour operator, represented by a ramified network of initiative tour companies, travel agencies, travel agents, subagents, distributors and other intermediaries. Today, Virtual Sector is the most promising and innovative means of electronic sales. It actively influences the meta-value of travel services operator and reduces not only the cost of the tour, but also the probability of error due to high technology and consolidation of sales processes of intermediaries.

Virtual processes have a very real cost, and the issue of commission to sales agents is determined by establishing a margin (agency remuneration), which is specified in the agency agreement, commission contract, concession contract (franchise) or a contract of sale.

The most powerful Internet-sector of sales operates with the capabilities of electronic booking systems, promotion and sales of travel services. Information support for such process innovations are:

- Global Distribution System (GDS), a combination of powerful professional booking and reservation systems for all types of travel services (Amadeus, Galileo, Worldspan, Travelport, Sabre, Serena);
- Alternative Distribution System (ADS) – alternative booking systems that are created as price aggregators and offer the possibility to book both package tours and individual services for intermediaries or direct clients (portals such as booking.com, expedia.com, tickets.ua, hotels.com., lastminute.com., ORBITZ and other online booking sites for travel services for end users and agencies);
- Central Reservation System (CRS) – centralized reservation system for solving electronic distribution problems. This highly-technological development is a marketing innovation and is intended for downloading information on hotel services (airlines, tour operators, etc.) into all existing electronic channels of sale in order to increase the efficiency of direct online sales from the site of the company.

This promotion program is closely integrated with the booking system and allows you to increase sales volumes from the site – Business Service Provider (BSP) (Business Service Provider) is a contextual B2 «Business for Business» Program, as a set of software products, combined features and capabilities of multimedia document management systems and office management process management systems to reduce redundancy in traditional document circulation and improving the effectiveness of administrative

work, which mainly work on the Microsoft software platform [8].

These information tools and resources help of the tourist enterprises in the implementation of administrative management create an intellectual environment at all levels of management activity; formulate intelligent application systems for working with the external environment of mobile users, business travel services and tourism. This increases the requirements for the staff of tourist offices, promotes the emergence of new positions: (e-Commerce Manager, e-Tourism Revenue Manager), and, consequently, the formation of new competencies of the manager-innovator.

The further development of the virtualization of the tour is directed at the widespread use of mobile technologies by tourists before, during and after the trip, as well as with the aim of finding the necessary information about the special offers of tour operators, contact information, taking part in the prize draw, additional tour services, etc.

Also, the new directions of using information technologies for tourism are: introduction of mobile Internet, electronic catalog of offers; distribution of online booking not only in working with retail agencies, but also directly with customers; fullness of sites for information on countries and new tourist routes, software and software solutions – these are just a few examples illustrating the innovative activity of tourism enterprises and the areas of its further development. The above trends require consumers to have some experience in travel, knowledge about the use of mobile and Internet technologies, as well as the high professional level of personnel of tourist intermediary organizations.

Conclusions. Quality of services sector affects on the structure of consumer demand and is an important factor in the competition in the tourism market in the current conditions of management. Tourists who are satisfied by service sector in hotels, restaurants, tour agencies, travel agencies, become their active propagandists. The quality of services sector is ultimately an important factor in improving the economic efficiency of tourism. On the quality of service is influenced by factors such as the complexity of services and goods, their direction on a particular consumer, the timeliness of their provision.

International integration in the system of tourism education through the introduction of innovative methods of education preparation professionals for the tourism industry and the creation of educational international clusters is directed at increasing the competitiveness of our graduates in the labour market, formation a career throughout life, providing students with practical preparation, their mobility and quality of education.

References

1. Astakhov A., Hryplyva L. *The system of quality management – an instrument for improving the general management system of organization (by enterprise) // Standardization, certification, quality. – 2011. – N. 4. – P. 60-64.*
2. Gutsol A. *Educational discipline «Innovative technologies in tourism» as an important component of preparation specialists sp. «Tourism Studies» // Journal of the LNU. Pedagogical science – 2012. – Is.4 (239). – P. 124-129.*
3. DSGU 9000-2007 «System of Quality Management. Basic Terms and Dictionary». – URL: document.ua/sistemi-upravlinnja-jakisty-u-osnovni-polozhennja-ta-slovnik-nor14237.html.
4. DSGU 9001-2009 «Systems of Quality Management Requirements». URL: www.ukrcsm.kiev.ua/index.php/uk/2009-02-12-13-16-36/63-2009-02-12-08-27-01/122-2009-02-19-13-37-47.
5. *Strategy of innovation development of Ukraine on 2010-2020 years in the context of globalization challenges of February 17, 2009 year № 965-VI* URL: [http // kno.rada.gov.ua/komosviti/control/ uk / publish / article? art_id](http://kno.rada.gov.ua/komosviti/control/uk/publish/article?art_id).
6. Lozovetska V. *Methodological approaches to the formation of career of future specialists // Scientific journal of Institute's professional education NAPS of Ukraine. Prof. Education: Collection of sciences works: Is. 8. - K.: «Polygraph Service», 2014. – P. 21–28.*
7. Mykhailichenko G. *Innovative development of tourism: monograph. – K.: KNETU, 2012. – 608 pp.*
8. *ISO 9001: 2008 Quality Management Systems – Requirements. – URL: www.iso.org/iso/catalogue_detail?csnumber=464864.*

Tanana Svitlana – Ph.D. in Pedagogy, Assistant Professor of the Department of Professional Education. (State Higher Educational Establishment «Pereiaslav-Khmelnytskyi State Pedagogical University named after Hryhoriy Skovoroda»).

Olena Sergiichuk – Ph.D. in Pedagogy, Assistant Professor of the Department of Professional Education. (State Higher Educational Establishment «Pereiaslav-Khmelnytskyi State Pedagogical University named after Hryhoriy Skovoroda»).